

Automatic Archery Scoring System Using Deep Learning and Image Processing

Haozhe Ma, Michael G. Madden

School of Computer Science, University of Galway

Abstract

This paper proposes an automatic archery scoring system that uses smartphone to read and record scores, addressing the limitations of existing manual and hardware-based scoring systems. Utilizing advancements in computer vision technology, the system consists of two main components: arrow localisation and arrow scoring. The localisation model uses a modified U-Net architecture to accurately identify the landing positions of arrows on a target, generating a saliency map that is converted into pixel coordinates essential for scoring. A custom dataset, which is released to public, was created to train this model. The scoring component identifies the target face using colour masking and applies image processing techniques for noise reduction and skew correction. It then matches the coordinates from the localisation model to the parameters of each scoring ring to calculate scores. While the model shows progressive improvement during training, further diversification of the dataset, exploration of alternate neural network architectures, and optimisation of hyperparameters can enhance accuracy. Future work includes improving front-end development for seamless functionality integration and adopting augmented reality (AR) for improved perspective correction.

Keywords: Deep learning, computer vision, image analysis, target recognition.

1 Introduction and Related Work

Archery has a long history as a weapon in combat and has evolved into a popular sport. In modern target archery, archers aim to hit a standardized circular target. The target faces, standardized by the World Archery Federation (WA or FITA), consist of concentric circles with assigned point values. When scoring arrows, if an arrow lands on the line between two rings, it is scored with the higher point. Many archers still manually record scores on paper or existing apps, which can be time-consuming and distracting. The goal of this work to develop an automatic archery system using smartphones to read and record scores.

Existing hardware-based archery scoring systems include FalcoEye [FalcoEye, 2012] and the RyngDyng system [RyngDyng Technology, n.d.]. The FalcoEye system utilizes laser technology and optical methods for accurate detection and visualization of hit points. The RyngDyng system uses cameras for precise arrow position measurement, requiring hardware setup and calibration. These systems are relatively heavy and expensive.

Previous projects have explored computer vision techniques for real-time archery scoring. Parag's approach in 2017 used a colour-based method and frame difference, but it struggled with lighting variations and object distinction [Parag, 2017]. His project employed the Hough line transform and contour testing to detect arrow shaft lines and intersections more accurately. Morphological operations were also proposed to obtain arrow outlines [Parag, 2017]. Other researchers have proposed a smartphone-based archery analysis system that utilizes machine learning-based object detection to locate arrows [Peng et al., 2021]. The image processing methods [Zin et al., 2013; Parag, 2017] relied on frame difference in videos to isolate arrows, which required fixing the camera position and implementing frame extraction algorithms. Furthermore, intricate geometric shape analysis was performed to detect arrow locations. However, our project aimed to devise a lightweight solution for automatic scoring, eliminating the need for supplementary tripod setups and utilizing users' mobile phone cameras. Nevertheless, we found the

approaches for target sheet detection and arrow scoring to be valuable, employing a similar image processing methodology.

2 Implementation

The system comprises two main components: arrow localisation and arrow scoring.

In the localisation component, pure image processing approaches show inconsistencies when there is a change in lighting condition and potential movements of camera. Parag [2017] requires a camera record video in fixed position to extract arrows from other objects. We decided to employ deep learning approach to make the localization simpler in implementation part and potentially able to handle more generalized real-world conditions. After conducting tests and experiments, we selected the architecture proposed by Ribera et al. [2019] for tasks such as crowd counting. They made slight modifications to the U-Net architecture to accommodate a single class object as input. Notably, their approach does not require bounding boxes during training data labelling and allows for a flexible number of inputs and outputs. These features make Ribera et al.'s architecture well-suited for this project's requirements, as the number of arrows shot onto the target can vary during training and competitions. Compared to generic object detection architectures like YOLO, Ribera et al.'s approach offers greater adaptability.

Through training, the neural network acquires the capability to accurately identify the exact location where each arrow lands on the target, which is commonly referred to as the intersection between the arrows and the target paper. Following the completion of training, the localisation neural network model is able to generate predicted locations for new images in the form of a saliency map, which can subsequently be converted into sets of pixel coordinates, as illustrated in the example in Figure 1. These coordinates play a pivotal role in furnishing the essential arrow positions for the scoring component of the system, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the mask for arrow scoring.

Creating a diverse and extensive training dataset was crucial for training the deep learning arrow localisation model. As there was no publicly available dataset containing archery target bosses, we captured 480 distinct images over training sessions, featuring various scores, arrow colours, perspectives, target backgrounds, and levels of target paper tear. Data labelling involved assigning point labels using the Label Studio tool, labelling each image with corresponding location coordinates and classes representing score values ranging from 1 to 10, along with a class for missed arrows. Data augmentation techniques, including rotation and random flipping, were applied to the original image set, resulting in an additional 86,400 images. Our dataset, consisting of accurately labelled FITA standard indoor targets, along with their scores, is publicly available on Google's Kaggle platform in JSON format under the CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 license [Ma, 2023].

The scoring component utilizes the standardised colours associated with different scoring rings on the target face. To identify the target face, the system employs a colour range to mask out specific colours, such as blue, from the target as shown in figure 2. Subsequently, upon locating one or more rings, the system applies a series of image processing techniques to reduce noise and correct any skew in the circles. This crucial step enables precise determination of the centroid corresponding to the bull's eye on the target face. With knowledge of the exact ring colour for detection,

Figure 1: Visualisation of the labelled points

Figure 2: Illustration of segmenting other rings relative to the outer ring ellipse. The centroid is marked with a blue dot.

the system then calculates the parameters of each ring and matches the coordinates predicted by the localization neural network to obtain the score for each detected arrow.

Finally, the system generates an output image that visualizes the predicted arrow locations and provides the corresponding scores in the user interface.

3 Experiments and Evaluation

Ribera et al. [2019] proposed a novel modified version of the average Hausdorff distance and called it the weighted Hausdorff distance (WHD):

$$d_{WH}(p, Y) = \frac{1}{S + \epsilon} \sum_{x \in \Omega} p_x \min_{y \in Y} d(x, y) + \frac{1}{|Y|} \sum_{y \in Y} M_\alpha [p_x d(x, y) + (1 - p_x) d_{max}]$$

where:

$$S = \sum_{x \in \Omega} p_x, \quad M_\alpha [f(a)] = \left(\frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{a \in A} f^\alpha(a) \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$$

Here, $d_{WH}(p, Y)$ is the weighted Hausdorff distance. During training, as shown in Figure 3, there are several loss terms displayed. Term 1 and Term 2 are the two terms to be summed for calculating weighted Hausdorff distance, respectively. Term 3 is the smoothed L1 loss for the regression of the object count, this is related to the number of ground truth points and the number of predicted points on the image, calculated by first subtract the estimated point number from ground truth number then perform regression. The final training loss is a combination of Term 1, Term 2 and Term 3, as the sum of the weighted Hausdorff distance and the regression term:

$$\mathcal{L}(p, Y) = d_{WH}(p, Y) + \mathcal{L}_{reg}(C - \hat{C}(p))$$

Figure 3: Training loss using original 480 images set

As can be seen in Figure 3, as the training progresses, the model exhibits increased confidence in accurately identifying the intersection points. This trend can be seen qualitatively in the saliency map shown in Figure 4, which shows that the model's ability to locate the intersection points on the target improves as training proceeds from 400 epochs to 1000 epochs. Throughout the training process, the training loss gradually decreased and reached a value below 10 at approximately 1000 epochs. At the point where we halted the

Figure 4: (Left) Saliency map produced during validation after around 400 epochs, the white points are ground truth. (Right) Localisation after around 1000 epochs of training.

training process, the model's performance was evaluated on a validation set that consisted of randomly torn target papers. The achieved recall and precision rates on this set were approximately 40%. Additionally, a separate test was conducted using five images with clean papers, similar to the illustration shown in Figure 4 (right). In this test, the model achieved a recall and precision rate of 100%, accurately identifying the positions of the arrows.

4 Conclusions, Limitations and Future Work

While the evaluation of the training process with existing dataset indicates progressive improvement in the detection results as training advances, it remains uncertain whether the current architecture can ultimately attain a level of accuracy that allows athletes to reliably substitute manual reading and counting tasks with this tool.

To improve the accuracy of the detection model, strategies include diversifying the training dataset by gathering a wider range of samples, exploring alternate neural network architecture like anchor-free YOLOv5, and further optimising hyperparameters such as the learning rate and optimizer choice.

Further front-end development is vital for the seamless integration of image capture, detection, and scoring functionalities. This necessitates additional research and training, particularly for enabling trained model accessibility across scripts and refining perspective correction to enhance bullseye detection accuracy.

Existing solutions, like Microsoft Office Lens, struggle with perspective correction when the target paper's colour resembles the background. An alternative could be Augmented Reality (AR) surface detection. Using frameworks like ARCore for Android and ARKit for iOS, the system could detect the target boss surface and overlay a virtual grid. This could offer a reference for perspective correction without needing to identify specific points, like target paper corners.

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